

PREPARATION OF SiC COATED CARBON FIBER BASED ON RAYON USING PSI PROCESSES

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SUMMARY: Based on high-strength rayon fiber, continuous SiC-coated carbon fibers were prepared. A chemical treatment using an amine-containing aqueous solution enables the fiber to be pyrolyzed at much higher heating rate. Multi-step pyrolysis accompanied with polymer solution infiltration processes using polycarbosilane solution was carried out. The pyrolysis temperature is up to 1000. The kinetics of the pyrolysis was investigated and a new model was proposed, with which, the pyrolysis procedure was established. The yield of the C/SiC fibers is 35-38%. The tensile strength of the fiber is 1.3-2.0GPa, Young's modulus of 70-130 GPa and average fiber diameter of 4 to 6 μ . Since the carbon and the exterior SiC are formed from the corresponding organic precursors at high temperature, the interface of C and SiC is formed by a strong linking and in a graduation form, with SiC infiltrated into the inner part of the fiber.

KEYWORDS: rayon, polycarbosilane, polymer-solution infiltration, carbon fiber, pyrolysis, amine-containing catalyst

INTRODUCTION

The preparation of carbon fibers based on rayon have been studied extensively since decades. It has long been recognized that, due to the structure of rayon, the carbon fibers resulted are of low yield, porous, and with lower mechanical properties than PAN-based fibers. The reason that rayon remains to be one of the widely used raw materials for producing carbon fiber is that rayon comes from regenerative natural resources and the resulted carbon fibers possess some characteristic properties to various applications [1], such as in activated carbon fibers [2] and some special composites, etc. In addition, with suitable technique, rayon can be modified by coating in the process of pyrolysis, which is unavoidably followed by a high weight loss, to improve the mechanical and electromagnetic properties.

Silicon carbide can be used as a protective coating on carbon fibers by CVD [3,4] and composites for anti-oxidation applications [5,6]. The precursor of SiC, polycarbosilane, is soluble in organic solvents [7] and it would be suitable for coating on the surface of fibrils. With the coating on rayon, or partly-pyrolyzed dark rayon, the interior cellulose turns into carbon while the exterior polycarbosilane becomes SiC by pyrolysis. The porosity and the irregular and indented cross section of the dark rayon allow an amount of polycarbosilane coated onto the surface and even infiltrated into the inner part of the fiber. The carbon and SiC will be linked strongly and the interface in gradient. The amount of SiC can be varied in a

range to adjust the properties of the C/SiC fiber. Actually, this method may be easily extended into another organic precursors to form different coatings.

EXPERIMENTAL

High strength rayon was applied as the raw material, which was washed continuously with acid, water and impregnated with an amine-containing aqueous solution. After drying in hot air, the fiber was pyrolyzed in steps. Low temperature pyrolysis was at 100°C and 250°C in air and 350°C and 500°C in nitrogen through tube-furnaces. The total time required was about 3 hours. When the weight loss of the fiber was in the range of 30-50%, a process of polymer solution infiltration (PSI) of the above dark fiber was carried out using a benzene solution of polycarbosilane, surface active agents and a catalyst in ultrasonic agitation at 60°C. To keep the concentration of the polymer solution unchanged in the PSI process, the solution was continuously replenished. Multi-cycle of PSI and low temperature pyrolysis was sometimes necessary to coat as more SiC as desired on the fiber. High temperature pyrolysis was taken place at 500°C, 700°C and 1000°C in nitrogen through silica glass tube-furnaces at a higher passing rate. The total time of the pyrolysis was less than 5 hours. SiC coated carbon (C/SiC) fibers were thus obtained. The procedure is schematically presented in Fig. 1. The structure of the fibers was characterized by SEM, IR spectroscopy, DTA/TG, X-ray diffraction of fiber and powder, element analysis and XPS etc.

Fig. 1 Flow chart of the preparation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Amines-containing Catalyst

To produce carbon fibers with high tensile strength from rayon, the low-temperature pyrolysis is usually at as low rate of heating as possible [8], due to a long time is required to moderate the chain splitting and the evaporation of the large amount of small molecules from the system. It has long been reported that the pyrolysis of rayon can be catalyzed by some chemicals, or flame retardants, such as those containing phosphorus, sulfur, halides and nitrogen etc. [9,10]. In this work, a chemical treatment using an aqueous solution containing polybasic amines and surface active agents was applied. This enables rayon to be pyrolyzed at a significantly higher heating rate, while the yield of the resulted carbon fiber is increased considerably.

It seems very complicated to explain the mechanism of the catalyst in details. What is clear is that, owing to the reactions of the amines with the primary hydroxyl group of the glucose repeat units in the fibril surface, the energy of activation of decomposition is much lower. The polybasic amines crosslink the macroradicals and a larger amount of char will be produced at lower temperature at the expense of harmful levoglucosan in the form of tar. The char in the fiber surface in turn protects the fiber from rush chain splitting and evaporation of the small molecules in the process of the next-step pyrolysis.

Fig. 2 is the TG and DTG profiles of rayon with the heating rate at 10°C/min. With the catalyst impregnation, the weight lose starts at a lower temperature (200°C) comparing with that without the treatment (290°C). DTG curve 3 shows that a new reaction takes place at low temperature, while a higher peak, which signifies the normal decomposition, appears at the same temperature with the sharp peak 4 of raw rayon. This also demonstrates that much higher residual weight of impregnated rayon left up to 600°C. This effect is somewhat equivalent to decreasing the heating rate (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2 The effect of the amines-containing catalyst on rayon. 1 and 2, TG with and without the catalyst; 3 and 4 DTG with and without the catalyst.

Fig. 3 The comparison of heating rate on TG and DTG profiles of rayon after impregnation.

Kinetics of the Low-temperature Pyrolysis

The kinetics of the pyrolysis, especially in low-temperature range in air, of rayon as well as the other cellulose materials has been studied by many authors [11,12]. However, there is a lot of different conclusions because of the complexity of the reactions involved. In this work, to establish the pyrolysis procedure, the kinetics was considered. As mentioned previously, the impregnation of the amines-containing catalyst accelerates the weight loss in the first-stage of pyrolysis. It would be very interesting to investigate the difference in their kinetic behaviors.

Millet [12] and Basch [13] investigated the weight loss (WI) of cellulose materials and found first-order kinetics, or

$$dWI/dt \propto -KWl.$$

However, this can hardly be used to depict the weight loss to a little longer time from the very beginning. Since the weight loss is started from the surfaced of the material, the weight loss must be a diffusion controlled reaction. The higher the weight loss, the more difficult the evaporation of the volatile components. Another term, that is similar to the diffusion from the film in surface condensation [14], should then be added to the equation, which is written as:

$$dWI/dt = K'/WI. - KWl$$

or

$$WI = (K'/K)^{0.5} (1 - e^{-2Kt})^{0.5}$$

Fig. 4 and 5 respectively show the isothermal weight loss at a few selected temperatures with and without the catalyst impregnation, and the data were emulated by the kinetic equation. The theory seems fit the weight loss of rayon studied even for a rather long time. It should be noted that the constant $(K'/K)^{0.5}$ is actually the maximum weight loss at a certain temperature.

Fig. 4 Isothermal weight loss curves for the catalyst-impregnated rayon

Fig. 5 Isothermal weight loss curves for rayon without catalyst-impregnation.

Fig. 6 and 7 show good linear relations which were used to the calculation of the activation energies. Table 1 summarizes the results of the kinetic analysis. With the impregnation, the two energies of activation decreased significantly.

Fig.6 Calculation of activation energies of weight loss of rayon with the catalyst-impregnation.

Fig. 7 Calculation of activation energies of weight loss of rayon without the catalyst-impregnation.

Table 1, The kinetics results of pyrolysis of rayon in air with and without the impregnation. (E: activation energy and A: frequency factor for K; those with prime corresponding to K')

Temp., °C	K, min ⁻¹	K', min ⁻¹	ΔE, KJ/mol	A	ΔE', KJ/mol	A'
with catalyst-impregnation						
150	0.050	32.51	8.91	0.60	42.09	4.0410 ⁶
200	0.065	100.39				
235	0.072	166.50				
without catalyst-impregnation						
220	0.005	0.168	32.67	13.25	130.16	1.0110 ¹³
250	0.006	0.953				
280	0.012	5.292				

The kinetics of the pyrolysis is a principle to establish the temperature program, passing rate and staying time of the fiber in the low temperature pyrolysis. While for high temperature pyrolysis, the temperature program were designed using a least square method.

PSI Process using Polycarbosilane Solution

After rayon fibers were pyrolyzed at low temperature, 200-300°C, the dark fibers were coated with polycarbosilane solution in benzene. The polymer solution infiltration process is very sensitive to the molecular weight and the concentration of the polycarbosilane as well as the composition of the solution used. In addition, the temperature and ultrasonic agitation of the process are also important.

To avoid the bonding between the fibrils, that will cause the fiber deteriorate in high-temperature pyrolysis, the molecular weight of polycarbosilane had to be limited to about 500°C to 1000°C and the concentration to 4-10%. In the polymer solution, surface active agents were added to disperse the polymer on the surface of fibrils. Crosslinking agent was also needed especially for low-molecular-weight polymer.

After the PSI process, the fiber was cured at elevated temperature in air for 10min and pyrolyzed at 300-400°C, followed by high temperature pyrolysis up to 1000°C. When more SiC was desired on the carbon fiber, more PSI and low-temperature pyrolysis cycles were taken. The content of SiC is about 3 to 8%.

The Structure of the C/SiC Fiber

From the SEM photograph in Fig. 8, the surface of the C/SiC fibers are smooth and no bonding between the fibrils. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the C/SiC fiber are shown in Fig. 9, there are at least three types of crystalline.

- (a) Two wide reflections belonging to carbon/graphite are found: 200 and 101. One can estimated the degree of graphite crystalline, g , by the d-spacing (in nm) of 200 reflection using equation proposed by Haraka and Warren [15],

$$d(002) = 0.3354g + 0.3440(1 - g)$$

The d-spacing is at 0.341 to 0.342nm, that means the degree of graphite crystalline is in the range of 23 to 35%.

- (b) There shows 3 reflections of β -SiC on the profiles taken on the fibers with additional non-stretch heating at 1700°C: 0.25nm (111), 0.21nm (220) and 0.15nm (311). However, for 1000°C fibers, these 3 reflections are not visible. That means the SiC crystalline is more difficult to form than polycarbosilane fiber. What is interesting is that for the commercial carbon fiber, such as T300, treated by the same PSI process and additional heating, the 3 reflections are not exist at all. This seems to be because the dense surface of the carbon fiber of T300 cannot be coated by polycarbosilane to a considerable amount, while for the dark rayon, the fiber surface is porous and rough and can hold much more polymer and shows SiC crystalline. High molecular weight in polycarbosilane is favorable for the formation of β -SiC.

Fig. 8 SEM photograph of C/SiC fiber

Fig. 9 X-ray diffraction patterns of C/SiC fiber.

- (c) There are 3 sharp reflections at 0.71nm, 0.64nm and 0.32nm that cannot be assigned to C/graphite or SiC. Those should belong to one of the oxides of silicon, SiO_x [16], which comes out from the oxidation of curing. But with polycarbosilane of higher molecular weight, the reflections are smaller.

Since the carbon and the exterior SiC are formed in the process of high-temperature pyrolysis, the interface of the C and SiC is not as sharp as ordinary coating of SiC on a carbon fiber by CVD method and so on. The fiber with a structure of gradient from carbon to SiC is characteristic of this process. Evidence for this was based on XPS, where Si was detected even at the center of the fibrils.

The Properties of the C/SiC Fiber

Pyrolyzed at 1000°C, the overall yield of the C/SiC fiber is 35-38% by weight related to the raw rayon. The typical average elemental contents of the fiber are made of C, 88%(w), Si, 5%, N, 3% and a certain amount of oxygen. Of the C/SiC fiber, the density is 1.55-1.60g/cm³, the tensile strength 1.3-2.0 GPa, the Young's modulus 70-130GPa, the average diameter 4 to 6 μ and the specific resistivity 10⁻² to 10⁻³ Ω cm. When the fibers were exposed at 400°C for 2 hours, the retention of the tensile strength as well as that of the weight of the C/SiC fiber is about 1.5 to 1.8 times of those of the fiber without SiC PSI treatment.

CONCLUSIONS

1. An amines-containing aqueous solution is very effective as catalyst of the pyrolysis of rayon. The impregnation of the catalyst on rayon not only accelerates the reactions, diminishing the pyrolysis time to 5 hours, but also results in a high yield, 35-38%(w), of the carbon fiber.
2. Polycarbosilane with a moderate molecular weight and concentration was coated on the surface of rayon fibrils by PSI processes. Carbon from the interior rayon and SiC from the exterior polycarbosilane are formed in the process of high temperature pyrolysis.
3. In the C/SiC fiber, carbon and SiC are linked strongly, and some SiC is infiltrated into the inner part, thus a gradient structure is assumed. The fiber after 1000°C pyrolysis contains 3-8%(w) of SiC and shows a tensile strength of 1.3-2.0 GPa and Young's modulus 70-130 GPa .
4. The weight lose kinetics of rayon is established from the experimental data that the weight lose (Wl) obeys the following relation.

$$dWl/dt = K'/Wl - KWl$$

The energies of activation were obtained.

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